

Biginelli reaction on 4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde – a search for reaction pathway

Chandrakanta Bandyopadhyay*, Partha Pratim Nag, Kumar Ranabir Sur, Ranjan Patra, Subhabrata Banerjee, Arunabha Sen and Tapas Ghosh*

Department of Chemistry, R. K. Mission Vivekananda Centenary College, Rahara, Kolkata-700 118, India

E-mail : kantachandra@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 31 January 2003, revised 6 May 2003, accepted 22 August 2003

On heating a mixture of 3-formylchromone **1**, active methylene compound **2** or **3** and urea (**4**) in AcOH produces dihydropyrimidinones **10** or **11**, whereas use of thiourea in place of urea produces 1,3-thiazine derivative **14** or **15** and the above reactions pass through the Knoevenagel condensate **5** or **6**.

Biginelli reaction¹ for the synthesis of dihydropyrimidinones is a one-pot condensation of ethyl acetoacetate, benzaldehyde and urea under acidic conditions. Its renewed interest in the last decade is mainly due to the close structural relationship of dihydropyrimidines to the clinically important dihydropyridine calcium channel modulators of the Nifedipine-type². Several improved procedures have recently been reported using BF₃³, clay (KSF)⁴, dry HOAc and microwave irradiation⁵, InCl₃⁶, BiCl₃⁷, ionic liquid⁸, LiClO₄⁹, Mn(OAc)₃¹⁰, Yb^{III} resin¹¹, NH₂SO₃H¹², ZnCl₂¹³ instead of usual mineral acid. Base catalysed^{5b} and soluble polymer supported¹⁴ syntheses of Biginelli compounds are also reported. 6-Formylvisnagin and 6-formylkhellin have been used in this reaction in place of benzaldehyde¹⁵. Despite the large improvement of the reaction procedure¹⁶, the mechanism of the reaction is still an open question. Of the three components, the initial interaction of aldehyde and urea was first proposed by Folkers and Johnson¹⁷ and later established by Kappe¹⁸. But Sweet and Fissekis¹⁹ proposed the initial combination of aldehyde and active methylene compound to form the aldol type intermediate. Though the title compound **1a** has been reported to react with ethyl acetoacetate and urea in the presence of piperidine in ethanol to produce the pyrimidinone **10a**^{5b}, but no comment has been made on the reaction pathway. We report herein the pathway of the above-mentioned reaction.

Results and discussion

On heating a mixture of aldehyde **1**, ethyl acetoacetate (**2**), and urea (**4**) in glacial acetic acid under reflux for 6 h produces dihydropyrimidinone **10** in 50–55% yield along

with a small amount of **12** (~5%). In search of the reaction pathway, condensate **5**²⁰ was prepared by base catalysed condensation of **1** and **2**. It was then allowed to react with urea in acetic acid. Surprisingly, dihydropyrimidinone **10** was obtained in 50–55% yield. In this context it should be mentioned that ethyl benzalacetoacetate and urea failed to produce the dihydropyrimidinone¹⁷. This is the first example where the Biginelli reaction has been shown to proceed via the Knoevenagel condensate. To check the feasibility of formation of the condensate **5** in reaction medium, a mixture of aldehyde **1a** and **2** in glacial acetic acid was heated under reflux for 5 h. Interestingly, **5a** was also produced in 55% yield.

In the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) the Knoevenagel condensate **5** is supposed to be formed first. Subsequently, 1,4-addition of urea to **5** takes place to form **8**. Stabilisation of the pyrone moiety via pyrylium ion **7** restricts the possibility of 1,6-addition²¹. Cyclisation of **8** gives **9**, which on dehydration produces dihydropyrimidinone **10**.

Considering the possibility of initial interaction of aldehyde and urea^{17,18} in this reaction, the reaction of **1** with urea in glacial acetic acid was performed. In fact, no pure compound could be isolated when a mixture of **1** and **4** was heated under reflux in glacial AcOH for 5 h. Again, a mixture of **1** (4 mmol) and **4** (6 mmol) was heated under reflux in AcOH for 4 h. Then the reaction mixture was divided into two parts. Ethyl acetoacetate (**2**) (2 mmol) was added to one part and both the reaction mixtures were further heated under reflux for 4 h. No change was observed after addition of **2** and also formation of **10** could not be detected by TLC.

Scheme 1

In most of the earlier reports^{3,6,19} more than stoichiometric amount of urea was used with one equivalent each of aldehyde and ethyl acetoacetate. To check the utility of this excess amount of urea, an equimolar amount of **1**, **2** and **4** in AcOH was heated under reflux for 5 h. The reaction mixture afforded **10** along with a small amount of **5**. This observation also supports the reaction to proceed via Knoevenagel condensate **5**. Though use of equimolar amounts of aldehyde, **2** and **4** by Kappe¹⁸ at RT shows a good yield (70–75%) of Biginelli's product, we did not get it probably due to the difference in reaction condition. The previous reaction was performed at RT, whereas the present reaction has been performed under hot condition. On heating under reflux, decomposition of urea may take place to liberate NH_3 . This NH_3 may interact with Knoevenagel condensation product **5**^{22,23}. Indeed, we obtained **13**²³ along with **11** when a mixture of **1**, acetylacetone (**3**) and urea (**4**) was heated in AcOH under reflux for 5 h. Condensate **6** also produces **11** and **13** when treated with urea. Formation of **12** can be explained by considering the formation of **12** (OH in place of OMe) by the interaction of enamine, generated from NH_3 and **2**, with **1**²³. The insertion of OMe in place of OH is due to the use of MeOH during work-up.

When a mixture of **1**, **2** and **4** or **5** and **4** in ethanol was heated under reflux for 8 h, only a poor yield (5–10%) of **10**

was obtained. This proves the necessity of acidic condition for the formation of **10** and the acidic condition may help to activate the olefinic bond of the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl moiety in **5**.

Use of thiourea in place of urea in this reaction fails to produce the desired Biginelli product. But 2-amino-1,3-thiazine **14** was obtained, which was also obtained when a mixture of **5** and thiourea in AcOH was heated under reflux for 6 h (Scheme 2). It is noteworthy that ethyl benzalacetate also reacts with thiourea to produce similar type of 2-amino-1,3-thiazine derivative¹⁸. Reaction of **1** with thiourea produces 5-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione²⁴. These reaction sequences also support the initial interaction of **1** and **2** to form the condensate **5** en route to **14**. Similarly, compound **15** was obtained from any of the reaction mixtures of **1a**, **3** and thiourea or **6a** and thiourea (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

In conclusion, Biginelli reaction on the title aldehyde proceeds through Knoevenagel condensate and not via initial aldehyde-urea interaction.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. ^1H NMR (300 MHz) spectra were run in DMSO- d_6 solution unless stated otherwise. J values are given in Hz. IR spectra were taken as KBr plates. 1,3-Dicarbonyl compounds, urea, thiourea and glacial AcOH were all of commercial grades. All liquid reagents were distilled before use. Light petroleum refers to the fraction with distillation range 60–80°.

Reaction of 1, 2 and 4 :

A mixture of 3-formylchromone **1** (2 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (**2**) (260 mg, 2 mmol) and urea (**4**) (180 mg, 3 mmol) in glacial AcOH (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h. After completion of reaction, AcOH was removed under reduced pressure. Crushed ice (25 g) was added to the residue, the deposited solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. It was then heated with MeOH under reflux for 30 minutes and filtered hot. The residue was crystallised from glacial AcOH using charcoal to afford a white solid **10** and the methanolic solution was chromatographed over silica gel (100–200 mesh). From the reaction of **1a**, **2**, and **4**, the methanolic solution produces **12a** (30 mg, 5%) using 25% benzene in petroleum ether. **10a** (340 mg, 51%), **10b** (380 mg, 56%) were obtained from **1a** and **1b**, respectively. **12b** could not be isolated.

5-Ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl-4-(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (10a) : M.p. 274° (rep.^{5b} 265°); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3250, 3115, 3000, 1700, 1650, 1400, 1220; δ_{H} 9.24 (1H, s, 1-H), 8.17 (1H, s, 2'-H), 8.07 (1H, dd, J 7.9 and 1.5, 5'-H), 7.80 (1H, m, 7'-H), 7.64 (1H, dd, J 8.3 and 1.8, 8'-H), 7.50 (1H, m, 6'-H), 7.25 (1H, d, J 2.1, 3-H), 5.22 (1H, d, J 2.1, 4-H), 3.98 (2H, q, J 7.0, OCH₂Me), 2.25 (3H, s, 6-CH₃) and 1.07 (3H, t, J 7.0, OCH₂CH₃).

5-Ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl-4-(6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (10b) : M.p. 296° (Found : C, 62.91; H, 5.25; N, 8.10. C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₅ requires : C, 63.15; H, 5.30; N, 8.18%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3236, 3115, 2981, 1706, 1641, 1483, 1220; δ_{H} 9.23 (1H, s, 1-H), 8.12 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.85 (1H, d, J 1.5 and 5'-H), 7.62 (1H, dd, J 8.5 and 1.5, 7'-H), 7.54 (1H, d, J 8.5, 8'-H), 7.24 (1H, d, J 2.1, 3-H), 5.23 (1H, d, J 2.1, 4-H), 3.96 (2H, q, J 7.0, OCH₂Me), 2.42 (3H, s, 6'-CH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, 6-CH₃) and 1.06 (3H, t, J 7.0, OCH₂CH₃); δ_{C} 175.5 (4'-C), 165.2 (CO₂Et), 154.5 (2-C), 154.1 (8a-C), 152.1 (6-C), 150.1 (2-C), 135.3 (5'-C), 135.1 (6'-C), 124.6 (3'-

C), 124.3 (7'-C), 123.5 (4'a-C), 118.3 (8'-C), 95.2 (5-C), 59.1 (OCH₂Me), 48.1 (4-C), 20.5 (6-CH₃), 18.0 (6'-CH₃) and 14.2 (OCH₂CH₃).

Ethyl 5-methoxy-2-methyl-5H[1]benzopyrano[4,3-b]pyridine-3-carboxylate (12a) : M.p. 118° (Found : C, 68.30; H, 5.75; N, 4.70. C₁₇H₁₇NO₄ requires : C, 68.21; H, 5.72; N, 4.67%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2999, 2964, 1720, 1604, 1587; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.42 (1H, dd, J 7.7 and 1.6, 10-H), 8.17 (1H, s, 4-H), 7.42 (1H, m, 8-H), 7.18 (1H, m, 9-H), 7.11 (1H, dd, J 8.4 and 1.8, 7-H), 6.05 (1H, s, 5-H), 4.39 (2H, q, J 7.2, OCH₂Me), 3.58 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.93 (3H, s, 2-CH₃) and 1.42 (3H, t, J 7.2, OCH₂CH₃).

Reaction of 5 and 4 :

A mixture of acrylate **5** (2 mmol) and urea (**4**) (180 mg, 3 mmol) in glacial AcOH (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h. Similar work-up as for the reaction of **1**, **2** and **4** afforded **10a** (345 mg, 52.5%) and **10b** (340 mg, 50%).

Reaction of 1, 3 and 4 :

A solution of a mixture of **1** (2 mmol), **3** (200 mg, 2 mmol) and **4** (180 mg, 3 mmol) in glacial AcOH (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h. Similar work-up procedure was followed. But extraction of the dried solid was made by benzene in place of MeOH as in the previous cases. Crystallisation of the residue from glacial AcOH afforded pyrimidinones **11a** (410 mg, 69%) and **11b** (450 mg, 71%). On chromatographic separation of the benzene solution produces **13a** (40 mg, 8%) and **13b** (30 mg, 6%).

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (11a) : M.p. 275° (Found : C, 64.50; H, 4.80; N, 9.41. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₄ requires : C, 64.42; H, 4.73; N, 9.39%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3370, 3227, 3101, 2951, 1750, 1637, 1464, 1234; δ_{H} 9.25 (1H, s, 1-H), 8.11 (1H, s, 2'-H), 8.08 (1H, d, J 8.1 and 1.8, 5'-H), 7.80 (1H, m, 7'-H), 7.63 (1H, dd, J 7.2 and 1.5, 8'-H), 7.50 (1H, m, 6'-H), 7.30 (1H, d, J 2.9, 3-H), 5.38 (1H, d, J 2.9, 4-H), 2.30 (3H, s, COCH₃) and 2.17 (3H, s, 6-CH₃).

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (11b) : M.p. 276° (Found : C, 65.30; H, 5.20; N, 8.91. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₄ requires : C, 65.38; H, 5.16; N, 8.97%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3373, 3296, 3119, 3067, 1701, 1647, 1483, 1242; δ_{H} 9.24 (1H, s, 1-H), 8.07 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.87 (1H, d, J 1.9, 5'-H), 7.63 (1H, dd, J 8.5 and 1.9, 7'-H), 7.54 (1H, d, J 8.5, 8'-H), 7.28 (1H, d, J 3.0, 3-H), 5.38 (1H, d, J 3.0, 4-H), 2.42 (3H, s, 6'-CH₃), 2.29 (3H, s, COCH₃) and 2.16 (3H, s, 6-CH₃).

3-Acetyl-5-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-2-methylpyridine (13a) : M.p. 134° (rep.²³ 135°); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 11.77 (1H, s,

exchangeable, OH), 8.88 (1H, d, *J* 1.7, 6-H), 8.28 (1H, d, *J* 1.7, 4-H), 7.60–7.53 (2H, m, 4'-H and 6'-H), 7.12 (1H, dd, *J* 8.3 and 1.8, 3'-H), 6.94 (1H, m, 5'-H), 2.86 (3H, s, CH₃) and 2.65 (3H, s, CH₃).

3-Acetyl-5-(2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoyl)-2-methylpyridine (**13b**) : M.p. 114° (rep. ²⁵ 115°); superimposable IR with an authentic sample prepared following the literature procedure²⁵.

Reaction of **6** and **4** :

Condensate **6**²⁰ (2 mmol) and **4** (180 mg, 3 mmol) were reacted using previous procedure. **11a** (298 mg, 50%), **13a** (100 mg, 20%) and **11b** (300 mg, 48%), **13b** (100 mg, 18%) were obtained from **6a** and **6b**, respectively.

Reaction of **1**, **2** and thiourea :

A mixture of **1** (2 mmol), **2** (260 mg, 2 mmol) and thiourea (228 mg, 3 mmol) in glacial AcOH (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h. Usual work-up was followed. Dried solid was extracted with benzene. The extract failed to afford any suitable compound but the residue on crystallisation from CHCl₃-light petroleum (charcoal) afforded **14a** (470 mg, 68%) and **14b** (500 mg, 70%) from **1a** and **1b**, respectively.

Ethyl 2-amino-4-methyl-6-(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-6*H*-1,3-thiazine-5-carboxylate (**14a**) : M.p. 232° (Found : C, 59.30; H, 4.61; N, 8.05. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₄S requires : C, 59.29; H, 4.68; N, 8.13%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3380, 3252, 3182, 2977, 1703, 1676, 1640, 1464; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.23 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6 and 1.8, 5'-H), 7.81 (1H, bs, NH), 7.70 (1H, m, 7'-H), 7.67 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.62 (1H, bs, NH), 7.47–7.41 (2H, m, 6'-H and 8'-H), 5.70 (1H, s, 6-H), 4.14 (2H, q, *J* 7.0, OCH₂Me), 2.45 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 7.0, OCH₂CH₃); δ_{C} 177.5 (4'-C), 176.1 (2-C), 165.3 (CO₂Et), 156.8 (8'a-C), 153.9 (2'-C), 146.3 (4-C), 134.6 (5'-C), 126.3 (3'-C), 126.0 (7'-C), 124.3 (4'a-C), 123.1 (6'-C), 118.6 (8'-C), 97.9 (5-C), 61.0 (OCH₂Me), 48.8 (6-C), 18.9 (4-CH₃) and 14.6 (OCH₂CH₃).

Ethyl 2-amino-4-methyl-6-(6-methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-6*H*-1,3-thiazine-5-carboxylate (**14b**) : M.p. 230° (Found : C, 60.25; H, 5.10; N, 7.80. C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₄S requires : C, 60.32; H, 5.06; N, 7.81%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3398, 3175, 3092, 2978, 1708, 1664, 1641, 1564, 1483; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.01 (1H, d, *J* 1.7, 5'-H), 7.75 (1H, bs, NH), 7.64 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.62 (1H, bs, NH), 7.50 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4 and 1.7, 7'-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8.4, 8'-H), 5.70 (1H, s, 6-H), 4.14 (2H, q, *J* 7.0, OCH₂Me), 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.18 (3H, t, *J* 7.0, OCH₂CH₃).

Reaction of **5** and thiourea :

Similar reaction procedure was followed to produce **14a**

(340 mg, 50%) and **14b** (360 mg, 51%) from **5a** and **5b**, respectively.

Reaction of **1a**, **3** and thiourea :

A mixture of **1a** (348 mg, 2 mmol), **3** (200 mg, 2 mmol) and thiourea (228 mg, 3 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 7 h. The solid left after the usual work-up and extraction with benzene, was crystallised from AcOH (charcoal) to afford a white solid **15** (500 mg, 80%).

5-Acetyl-2-amino-4-methyl-6-(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-6*H*-1,3-thiazine (**15**) : M.p. 252° (Found : C, 61.06; H, 4.50; N, 8.89. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₃S requires : C, 61.13; H, 4.49; N, 8.91%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3420, 3260, 3200, 3000, 1648, 1610, 1560, 1470; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.23 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8 and 1.8, 5'-H), 8.18 (1H, bs, NH), 7.75 (1H, bs, NH), 7.70 (1H, m, 7'-H), 7.67 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.48–7.43 (2H, m, 6'-H and 8'-H), 5.73 (1H, s, 6-H), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.22 (3H, s, CH₃).

Reaction of **6** and thiourea :

Similar reaction procedure was followed as in the previous case to produce **15** (450 mg, 72%) from **6a**.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance; Bose Institute, Kolkata for ¹H NMR spectral analyses. We are grateful to Prof. C. K. Ghosh, Department of Biochemistry, Calcutta University for helpful discussion and to Swami Shukadevananda, Principal, R. K. Mission Vivekananda Centenary College, Rahara, Kolkata for providing research facilities and continuous encouragement.

References

1. P. Biginelli, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1893, **23**, 360; *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1317.
2. S. Goldman and J. Stoltefuss, *J. Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 1559.
3. E. H. Hu, D. R. Sidler and U.-H. Dolling, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 3454.
4. F. Bigi, S. Carloni, B. Frullanti, R. Maggi and G. Sartori, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 3465.
5. (a) J. S. Yadav, B. V. S. Reddy, E. J. Reddy and T. Ramalingam, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2000, 345 and references therein; (b) B. Kumar, B. Kaur, J. Kaur, A. Parmar, R. D. Anand and H. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2002, **42**, 1526; (c) M. Kidwai, S. Saxena, R. Mohan and R. Venkatramayan, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2002, 1845.
6. B. C. Ranu, A. Hazra and U. Jana, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 6270 and references therein.

7. K. Ramalinga, P. Vijayalakshmi and T. N. B. Kaimal, *Synlett*, 2001, 863.
8. J. Peng and Y. Deng, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 5917.
9. J. S. Yadav, B. V. S. Reddy, R. Srinivas, C. Venugopal and T. Ramalingam, *Synthesis*, 2001, 1341.
10. K. A. Kumar, M. Kasturaiah, C. S. Reddy and C. D. Reddy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7873.
11. A. Dondoni and A. Massi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7975.
12. T. Jin, S. Zhang, S. Zhang, J. Guo and T. Li, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2002, 37.
13. C. V. Reddy, M. Mahesh, P. V. K. Raju, T. R. Babu and V. V. N. Reddy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 2657.
14. M. Xia and Y. -G. Wang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 7703.
15. N. M. Fawzy, A. H. Mandour and M. A. Zaki, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 2000, **43**, 401.
16. (a) C. O. Kappe, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 879; (b) J. Lu, B. -Q. Yang, Y. -J. Bai and H. -R. Ma, *Chienese J. Org. Chem.*, 2001, **21**, 640.
17. K. Folkers and T. B. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3784.
18. C. O. Kappe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1997, **62**, 7201.
19. F. Sweet and J. D. Fissekis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 8741.
20. W. D. Jones and W. L. Albrecht, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1976, **41**, 706.
21. C. Bandyopadhyay, K. R. Sur and R. Patra, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2002, 414; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 2002, 931.
22. G. Hass, J. L. Stanton, A. von Sprecher and P. Wenk, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 607.
23. C. K. Ghosh, A. Ray and A. Patra, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2001, **38**, 1459.
24. C. Pene and M. Hubert-Habart, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1980, **17**, 329.
25. C. K. Ghosh and S. Khan, *Synthesis*, 1981, 903.